

THE ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF CHROMIUM AND COBALT CHLORIDE

BY BHOLANATH GHOSH

The absorption maxima of the aqueous solutions of CrCl_3 and CoCl_2 have been measured, in or without the presence of the added impurities of KCl or Cl_2 and also in presence of electric and magnetic fields. Judging from the agreement of the values of wave numbers of these maxima with the term differences of the relevant ions, it is concluded that in the aqueous solutions both singly and multiply charged ions exist in equilibrium and this state is disturbed by the presence of the electric and magnetic fields and also by the addition of impurities. The shifts of the position of the bands arising from the different types of changes of environment round the ions are also recorded.

The problem of the colour of the inorganic salts have not as yet been solved in a satisfactory manner. The salts in solution generally possess the same colour as in crystals. Joos (*Ann. Physik*, 1926, 11, 1076) explains that the colour formation arises from aqua-complexes. Saha (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U. P.*, 1931, 1, 1) traces the origin of colour in the dissolved free ions, because he finds that the frequency difference between two absorption maxima coincides with the term difference of two deepest levels of the ions Kato (*Sci. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Japan*, 1930, 13, 232), Bose (*Z. Physik*, 1933, 18, 361, 376), and Karim and Samuel (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U. P.*, 1934, 3, 157) also hold the same view. From a study of the absorption maxima of aqueous solutions of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Karim and Samuel opine that the ions Cr^{+3} , Cr^{+2} and Cr^+ co-exist simultaneously in the solvated condition in the solution. Bose and Mukherji (*Phil. Mag.*, 1938, 26, 757; *Indian J. Phys.*, 1939, 13, 219) have applied Van Vleck's theory to explain the formation of the absorption spectra of paramagnetic salts or their complexes. The purpose of the present paper is to see how the position of the absorption bands change with the temperature, with the addition of minute traces of impurities and also under the application of the electric and magnetic fields.

EXPERIMENTAL

The spectrophotometer, described by the author elsewhere (*Current Sci.*, 1941, 10, 325) was used for this investigation in the visible region. The white light from a point-o-lite, after passing through the cell falls on the upper split-slit of a Hilger constant deviation spectrometer. Below this slit there is another half-slit, in the same vertical line, on which the light from a tungsten filament lamp could be projected with the help of a totally reflecting prism. The width of the lower slit was varied by a calibrated screw-head containing fine graduations and hence the intensity of the lower beam was adjusted to any arbitrary value. A small strip of the same range of wave-length from both spectra is sorted out by a slit in the field of view of the observing telescope and matched. Two cells of different thickness were used for the determination of the extinction coefficient. The temperature of the cell was varied by putting it in an air thermostat, having proper holes for the passage of light. For the ultraviolet region the method of photographic photometry was adopted using a hydrogen continuum as a source. A series of intensity marks were given by altering the width of the slit in the ratio 1 : 8 : 40 : 100. The time of exposure of the intensity marks and the absorption spectra were kept the same. The intensity of the light passing through the step-slit was varied by putting neutral ground glass filters in the path of the beam. The plates were microphotometered with a Zeiss recording microphotometer and the photographic density of the spectra and the calibrating marks were determined at various wave-lengths.

For applying the magnetic field the cell was placed in between the parallel pieces of a large electromagnet, where field upto 30,000 Gauss could be produced. For applying the electric field the cell was put between two parallel plates 10 cm. apart. Direct electric field of 40 K. V. per cm. is applied between them from a transformer using a mechanical rectifier, as used with an X-ray plant. The light travelled as a parallel beam through the cell in the electric or magnetic field, perpendicular to the lines of forces.

The data obtained with the aqueous solution of CrCl_3 and CoCl_2 under various conditions are given in Table I. The strength of the CrCl_3 solution was $1/50N$ and that of CoCl_2 $1/10 N$.

TABLE I

Solution.	Added salt or element.	Temp.	Electric or magnetic field.	Position of absorption bands in $m\mu$						Strength of the added salt or element.
				1st.	2nd.	3rd.	4th.	5th.	6th.	
CrCl_3 $N/50$	—	24.1	—	670	608	583	516	440	308	
	—	54.2	—	685	620	596	530	445	320	
	—	95.0	—	698	634	606	545	442	310	
	Cl_2	25.0	—	652	582	564	524	450	301	$N/1000$
	Cl_2	25.0	—	644	564	550	524	446	294	$N/240$
	KCl	25.0	—	684	620	595	520	447	315	$N/1000$
	—	26.0	H = 25000 Gauss	662	593	565	508	438	362, 336	
	—	25.8	E = 5K.V. per cm.	662	571	543	441	312	222	
CoCl_2 $N/10$	—	23.2	—	562	501	432	320			
	—	55.0	—	572	521	448	322			
	—	94.0	—	584	532	477	321			
	Cl_2	26.0	—	550	486	412	318			$N/400$
	Cl_2	25.0	—	541	475	401	306			$N/100$
	KCl	27.2	—	552	489	422	323			$N/3000$
	—	25.8	H = 25000 Gauss	575	485	455	410			
	—	26.2	E = 5K.V. per cm.	360	472	420	310	318		

DISCUSSION

The effect of increasing temperature is to shift the position of the bands to regions of longer wave-length. It is possible that all the ions in solutions exist in a loosely hydrated condition and that some part of the thermal energy is used up in breaking assunder these weak hydration bonds, before they are raised to states of higher quantum energy. The increasing temperature supplies greater thermal energy to these loose complexes helping their thermal disruption and hence the photonic energy subtracted from the continuum becomes less. This is why on increasing the temperature the degree of hydration becomes less.

The addition of KCl and Cl_2 shifts some of the bands towards the ultraviolet and others towards the red region.

The absorption bands are related to the term difference of the ions as described in the introduction.

In the case of CrCl_3 , the magnetic field shifts all the bands towards the ultraviolet, excepting the band at $308 m\mu$, which is shifted towards the red and is broken into two components 362 and $336 m\mu$. For CoCl_2 , the band $562 m\mu$ is shifted to $575 m\mu$; 501 to $485 m\mu$. The absorption maximum $432 m\mu$ is broken into two components 455 and $410 m\mu$; and the maximum 320 goes to $318 m\mu$.

The electric field shifts all the bands of CrCl_3 towards the ultraviolet very distinctly. For CoCl_2 also, the displacements of the bands are in the same sense, but the shifts are not so characteristic. The explanation of these shifts is difficult and more data are necessary before any theory can be built up explaining their origin.

It may be noted that the calculated χ_m value for none of the single or resonating structures, excepting case A with H-bonds, approaches the experimental value; the somewhat close approach of calculated χ_m value for case A with H-bonds to the experimental value loses its significance because X-ray study has shown that case B with H-bonds should represent the actual state of the urea molecule.

Clow, however, is of opinion that since there is no molecule containing $>C=O$ group in which the resonance

is prohibited, the calculation of diamagnetic susceptibility for such molecules already involves this resonance in the bond depression for $>C=O$; hence, in the susceptibility calculation such resonance should not be considered.

On this view, Clow has assigned the non-resonating structure (V) to the tetra-substituted ureas, the calculated molecular susceptibilities for such structures being in agreement with the experimental values. But he rules out the carbamide structure

(I) for ureas, as the calculated χ_m value without considering the above type of resonance (*viz.*, between structures I and III) does not agree with the experimental value. The equal resonance of $>C=O$ group between the double bonded structure and the single co-valent structure arising out of the splitting of the double bond, has, on the other hand, been particularly considered by Gray and Cruickshank themselves in the case of carboxylic acids (*loc. cit.*) in order to obtain agreement between the experimental and the calculated χ_m values. Thus we find that two contradictory hypotheses are necessary to obtain agreement between the experimental χ_m value and that calculated by Gray and Cruickshank's method in the two cases discussed above.

Clow has also considered two other structures, (VI) and (VII), the amino-imino structure (VI) resonating equally between the forms (VIa) and (VIb), and the zwitterion structure VII (originally suggested by Werner) resonating equally between the forms (VIIa) and (VIIb). Table II shows the calculated χ_m values for the different structures of urea considered by Clow. Since the mean χ_m calculated for the zwitterion structure (VII) is in agreement with the experimental value, this structure for urea has

been accepted by Clow. It may be remarked that such a structure of urea can be definitely ruled out from the results of X-ray analysis; moreover, in calculating the χ_m values, Clow has not considered the effect due to H-bonds which are most certainly present in the urea crystal. Furthermore, equal contribution to the normal state of the molecule by structures (VIIa) and (VIIb), even in such a molecule cannot be justified, as the structure (VII b) must be unstable due to its having smaller number of co-valent bonds and to the juxtaposition of positive charges.

TABLE II

Structure.	Form a.	Form b.	Mean.
I	27.46	—	27.46
VI	25.75	37.63	31.69
VII	27.90	38.80	33.35

The amino-imino structure (VI) for urea might as well be made to account for the experimental χ_m value on the assumption of 34% contribution by (VIa) and 66% by (VIb) to the normal state of the molecule. The postulate of equal resonance in every case between the double-bonded structure and the single-bonded structure resulting from the splitting of the double bond seems to be *ad hoc* and unjustified, and in this particular case of urea, in fact, has no realistic basis.

Clow has calculated the χ_m value of mono-, di- and tri-substituted ureas for different structures (non-resonating carbamide, resonating amino-imino- and resonating zwitterion) by Gray and Cruickshank's method and has compared the values with the experimental ones; this has led to the conclusion that the resonating zwitterion structure of urea undergoes gradual transition to the non-resonating carbamide structure of tetra-substituted ureas through the amino-imino structures in mono-, di-, and tri-substituted ureas. The method of calculation employed by Clow in these cases also involves all the arbitrariness already pointed out in the case of urea; hence the agreement of the experimental χ_m values with the calculated ones, in these cases as well, cannot be taken as an evidence of the reliability of Gray and Cruickshank's method as applied to resonating structures. The transition from zwitterion structure of urea to the carbamide structure through the amino-imino structure due to progressive substitution of H atoms in urea by heavier groups has little structural evidences except the enforced agreement of the diamagnetic susceptibility values. As has already been mentioned, the structure of urea itself in the solid state, has been found to differ entirely from that assigned by Clow.

Nevertheless, it cannot be denied that Gray and Cruickshank's method in the cases of resonating molecules like these, as has been pointed out by Siddhanta and Ray (*loc. cit.*), shows a decided improvement upon Pascal's method, though it fails to reproduce the experimental value within a limit to justify its adoption.

My grateful thanks are due to Prof. Priyadarajan Ray of the Calcutta University for his kind interest and guidance during the preparation of this paper. I also thank Dr. M. Ahmed, Principal, Rajshahi College, for the facilities to carry out the work.